

THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTISTIC SKILL IN TRANSLATION

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Annotation. *This article analyzes the importance of translation and artistic skill in the translation process, examines the difficulties that arise during this process, and explores the requirements for a translator’s artistic skill. The significance of a translator’s artistic skill in translation, as well as the factors influencing it, are discussed. The importance of artistic skill in translation is highlighted through examples of successful translations. Additionally, the challenges in demonstrating artistic skill are addressed.*

Keywords: *translation, artistry, translator, culture, lexical meaning, cultural contexts.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tarjima va tarjimada badiiy mahoratning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi, bu jarayonda yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va tarjimonning badiiy mahoratiga bo‘lgan talablar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Tarjimada tarjimonning badiiy mahoratining ahamiyati, shuningdek, badiiy mahoratga ta’sir etuvchi omillar xususida fikr yuritildi. Tarjimada badiiy mahoratning ahamiyati yutuqlari misolida yoritildi. Shuningdek, badiiy mahoratni namoyon etishdagi qiyinchiliklar xususida to‘xtalib o‘tildi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *tarjima, mahorat, tarjimon, madaniyat, leksik ma’no, madaniy kontekstlar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется значимость перевода и художественного мастерства в переводческом процессе, рассматриваются трудности, возникающие при этом, и исследуются требования к художественному мастерству переводчика. Обсуждается роль художественного мастерства переводчика в переводе, а также факторы, влияющие на него. Важность художественного мастерства в переводе иллюстрируется примерами успешных переводов. Кроме того, рассматриваются проблемы, связанные с проявлением художественного мастерства.*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, художественное мастерство, переводчик, культура, лексическое значение, культурные контексты.*

In today’s era of globalization, cultural, economic, and political ties between people are intensifying. In this process, the means of connecting languages - **translation** - is of paramount importance. Translation is not only the art of translating text from one language to another, but also the art of conveying content, culture, and historical context.

Translation can take various forms: oral, written, synchronous, coherent, artistic, scientific-technical, legal, and others. All of them require a unique approach, linguistic knowledge and cultural thinking.

- **Oral translation** is done in real time and is often used in political meetings, conferences, and court proceedings.
- **Written translation** is based on the text and requires deep analysis and accuracy.
- **Literary translation** requires a creative approach, literary style, and preservation of the spirit of the original work.

A translator is a person who connects not only two languages, but also two cultures. It acts as a mediator between language and culture, and incorrect translation can lead to serious

misunderstandings, even political conflicts. Therefore, the translator should not be limited to grammatical knowledge, but should be able to deeply understand the context.

Despite the development of information technologies and the creation of automatic translation systems based on artificial intelligence, the role of the human translator remains high. Machines can translate grammatically correctly, but they cannot accurately grasp subtle meanings, intonation, irony, or context. Translation is not just a change in language, but a process of transmitting spiritual wealth, ideas, and worldview. A good translation strengthens mutual understanding between peoples, while a poor translation can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts. Therefore, translation remains an important factor in the development of cultural relations.

Translation is not only a linguistic transformation, but also a key factor in intercultural communication. Each language expresses its own unique worldview, history, and mentality. For example, although the concept of "hospitality" in the Uzbek language exists in other languages, it is not always easy to fully reflect its deep social roots. Therefore, the translator must have a deep understanding not only of the language, but also of the culture, customs, and values of the people. The goal of translation should not be limited to adapting the text only to the reader's level of perception, but should be aimed at taking measures to recreate the content, methodological, stylistic, and artistic value of the original without causing the slightest damage. Otherwise, attractiveness and influence of the text in the original language will lose its power in the translated text. The next stage after the re-expression process is the artistic identification of the translation. This is a process of refinement and editing aimed at ensuring the equivalence of the ideological and artistic content, functional-stylistic, and semantic content of the original in the target language. (Sirojiddinov Sh., Odilova G. 2011)

Today, artificial intelligence and machine translation systems are rapidly entering the field of translation (Google Translate, DeepL, ChatGPT, etc.). These systems may surpass humans in speed and convenience, but they still do not fully understand the context. A human translator translates taking into account intonation, emotions, and cultural nuances. Therefore, a modern translator must be able to work with technologies, but also clearly know their capabilities and limitations.

Peter Constantine, director of the literary translation program at the University of Connecticut, emphasizes that machines must also find a suitable style for successful literary translation. Considering the inherent indeterminacy of words and the flexibility of literary language, we see that the machine still needs human guidance. Neural Machine Translation – (NMT) cannot replace living translators, but it can become a useful tool for translating literature. The interaction between machine and human translations is of great importance. Professional translators who understand the problems of machine translation can edit the original version of machine translation. Simple subsequent editing can correct minor spelling errors and improve grammar, while deep editing can solve more serious problems such as sentence structure and speech style. (Kurbanova Sh. 2025)

Achievements of artistic skill in translation

The art of translation has developed since ancient times as an integral part of human culture. Translation plays an important role in establishing connections between different nationalities and facilitating the processes of knowledge exchange. Translation can be understood not only as changing the language, but also as interpreting the culture and spirit of one language in another language, teaching another world. Especially when translating literary works, it is necessary to

take into account the artistic skills of the translator, his understanding of linguistic and intercultural differences, and specific aspects. The translator’s artistic skill is based not only on linguistic knowledge, but also on their creative thinking, aesthetic sensitivity, and ability to understand cultural differences. When translating a literary work in a unique way, the translator takes into account many aspects:

Aesthetic task: The translator’s goal is to preserve the aesthetic value of the original work.

Emotional and psychological impact: The translator must correctly convey the psychological and emotional impact of the literary work.

Prepared translation techniques: The translator must use language, style, and literary elements artistically.

When translating literary works, not only the grammatical structure and lexical meaning of the language are important, but also its aesthetic and spiritual content. A high level of artistic skill is required in the translation process, since the translation of works of art into an alternative language presupposes the preservation of their original meaning, feeling, aesthetic value, and cultural features.

Metaphors, artistic images, musical rhythms, and specific language tones used in literary works require a creative approach from the translator. The translator should not only translate words from one language to another, but also interpret artistic and emotional meanings. Literary translation is not just the translation of words, but also the reflection of the spirit of the original work in another language, taking into account a number of cultural, historical, and social contexts.

Differences between cultural contexts are one of the problems that arise in the translation process, and the translator may be forced to adapt the text to make it understandable in accordance with the acquired culture. Therefore, the correct understanding of the cultural context and its correct application to the translation process is one of the main tasks of the translator. To explain the role of cultural context in the translation process, several examples and quotes can be cited. These examples show how cultural differences affect the translation process: Cultural context in the translation of idioms.

English idiom: It’s raining cats and dogs.

This phrase, when translated directly, means “Mushuklar va itlar yomg‘ir bo‘lib yog‘moqda” but in English it simply means that it is raining heavily. Since it is not expressed in this way in Uzbek culture, the translator should adapt this phrase as “heavy/strong rain is falling” –kuchli yomg‘ir yog‘moqda” yoki “yomg‘ir sharros quymoqda” (Mamadaliyev A.M. 2024)

Main features of artistic skill in translation

Creative approach. The translator’s creative approach is crucial in translating literary works. When translating literary works, the translator often needs to use special vocabulary and stylistic devices, through which the original spirit of the work is reflected in another language. This process tests the translator’s artistic skills.

Understanding Intercultural Differences. When translating literary works, it is necessary to understand cultural differences. Every nation has its own unique worldview, values, and traditions. When translating literary works, the translator must preserve the original meaning and emotions of the work, taking these differences into account. This requires the translator’s intercultural knowledge and experience.

Emotional and Aesthetic Basis. Literary works often have a strong emotional and aesthetic impact. The translator must not only translate correctly in terms of language and grammar, but

also feel the aesthetic value and emotional uniqueness of the work. Such an approach to literary translation helps to preserve the feeling and tone of the original work.

Creative Translation Methods. A translator can use various creative methods when translating a literary work. This depends on the translator’s creative abilities, the use of words in preferred contexts, and the preservation of stylistic aspects and tones. Also, to preserve the uniqueness of literary works, the translator must sometimes be ready to make discoveries and innovations.

Difficulties of Artistic Skill in Translation

The more complex the phenomenon of translation itself, which is closely related to the bilateral linguistic-creative process, the more troublesome and problematic is the analysis of the skill of the creator who is active in this field. (Salomov G’. 1979).

Difficulties in the Translation of Metaphors. Metaphors, figurative expressions, and images frequently used in literary works require more attention to translation. Metaphors and images may not create the same meaning and image in different cultures. In this case, the translator, using their creative approach, is forced to create new metaphors to preserve the meaning and feeling of the original work in the new language.

Lexical Correspondence. Some words or phrases may not be correctly translated into another language. This situation creates uncertainties and difficulties for the translator, since each language has its own lexical system and cultural indicators. This problem in literary translation depends on the translator’s deep knowledge of the language and the effective use of its artistic possibilities.

Changing Cultural Context in Translation. Each culture has distinctly understood symbols, customs, and social contexts. The translator should try to “adapt” these cultural elements to another language, since some cultural features may not be translated directly. For example, many terms in Uzbek literature can be difficult to fully translate into English.

In conclusion, the translation process is more than just a change in language, it is a complex process related to the culture, history, emotions, and aesthetics of people. The artistic skill of the translator, his creative approach, and understanding of intercultural differences play an important role in preserving the original spirit of the work of art. Difficulties and ambiguities arising in the process of literary translation can be overcome with a high level of skill and experience of the translator. Therefore, developing the artistic skills of translators and supporting their creative approach will further enrich literary connections and intercultural understanding.

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